

Nonverbal Communication (NVC) And Teacher Presence In Collaborative Online Learning In Primary School

Ayşegül Liman Kaban

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: October 01,2025</p> <p>Accepted: January 02,2026</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Online Learning, Social Presence, Teaching Presence, Engagement, Motivation, Nonverbal Communication</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18133290</p>	<p><i>Communication process requires a powerful combination of verbal and nonverbal processes that is one of the abilities that every teacher needs to master. In communication, the estimation of sixty-five to seventy percent of the message is received by nonverbal and only thirty to thirty-five percent by verbal communication. This research seeks to analyze the effect of nonverbal communication by primary teachers on the motivation and presence of students in a collaborative online learning environment. The information was gathered by questionnaires and interviews from both instructors and learners. Qualitative research methods were used in this study. The results showed that Nonverbal Communication can be an essential source of inspiration and attention for the learning process of students and a medium to attract their attention. Relying on the research outcomes that show the important role of Nonverbal Communication (NVC) in the teaching and learning process teachers by using the appropriate NVC types, eventually, play a critical role during online collaborative teaching which can affect students' motivation and higher collaborative learning participation. To accurately convey learning content to students, teachers will have to improve and expand positive interactions.</i></p>

Introduction

The role of nonverbal communication in education during pandemic

Online learning is an up-to-date subject for all of the researchers and also for teachers in those days since all of the World is in pandemic because of Covid-19 since the early of 2020. This rapid change in education has had serious effects on learning such as decreasing motivation of students, lack of collaborative learning, and interaction between the teachers and students. Over a long period, when we speak about human communication, just language comes to our mind instantly, whereas nonverbal communication is widely overlooked (Manusov, 2016; Mehrabian, 1981). Communication theorists believe that verbal messages are expressed in the meaning of words, while non-verbal messages are passed on beyond the certain meaning of the words, and they show mostly feelings, personalities, and points of view. Nonverbal communication plays a major part in the teaching process of learning (Bunglowala&Bunglowala, 2015, p. 371). Immediate cues of the NVC for example eye contact, smiling, the pose of the body, gestures, and use of physical space enhance learning and interestingness (Andersen et al., 1979). According to Devito (2007) and Richmond and McCroskey (2000), the teacher needs to know and possess all methods of communication to develop successful teaching and achieve ideal learning success because they are mutually complementary. Indeed, the NVC influences the efficiency of the instructor's verbal communication. A lack of NVC by teachers, especially during the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, was also identified as an important challenge for students (Khalil et al., 2020).

The COVID-19 pandemic influenced life in all aspects, especially in education. After it gets worst, the global lockdown turned into schools' lockdown. This lockdown ended in a stressful situation for instructors and students with extremely limited options. All schools were shifted to online learning within days without preparation for this online learning situation. This huge unplanned shift from traditional learning to a completely online learning environment has changed the learning/teaching methods and priorities of schools and teachers in delivering the courses for their students (Khalil et al., 2020).

The interaction among learners is very important in online environments for student achievement (Akyol& Garrison, 2008; Richardson et al., 2017). Garrison et al., (2000) found that the scheme of the survey community, which identifies three basic elements (cognitive presence, social presence, and educational presence) is accustomed to deliver a significant learning experience. While social presence plays a significant role under normal circumstances, its position shifts significantly during the pandemic period in an epidemic outbreak (Liman Kaban, 2021). In the expected results of learning, communication models used by primary teachers play a strategic role (Allen et al., 2006) and it has also been proven that the results of the immediate NVC are positively associated with higher levels of student motivation.

The relationship between NVC and social presence in a collaborative online learning environment

The growing collaboration among learners impacts the degree to which learners view themselves as true individuals, in other words, it affects their feelings of social presence positively (Hackman & Walker, 1990). Students suggest greater enjoyment in the classroom and improved expectations of having learned from the instructor as teachers attempt to use immediate non-verbal communication techniques (Griffin, 1985). In particular, teachers' use of the NVC is interesting because, in the early years of primary school, children begin to understand, process, and use the NVC. Teachers provide role models for the NVC but if the NVC of the teacher is different from his or her verbal communication, the true meaning of the communication can be difficult for children to process.

The NVC in interactive online learning affects the motivation, level of commitment, and understanding of students

The quality of learning in children depends intensely on the quality of interaction between themselves and the teacher, and as children's lexicon and level of understanding are restricted, NVC shapes much of this interaction. Body language can be an efficient attitude and affirmation method for representing (Wolfgang, 1977). Using eyes, imitations, and movements help teachers to create a relationship with learners; Marshall and Rossman (1989) also added that to build a persuasive yet not confusing effect on the students, teachers need to coordinate their body language, eye contact, speaking voice, and appearances. The objective of these studies was to investigate how nonverbal communication (NVC) and teacher presence in collaborative online learning can affect students' motivation and learning outcomes in primary school.

The goal of this study is to gain an understanding of the nonverbal communication and teacher presence effects on collaborative online learning environments. In line with the objective of this study aimed to answer the research questions:

Is there a relationship between NVC and social presence in a collaborative online learning environment?

Bearing in mind the lack of body language, is Nonverbal Communication which relates to teacher' and learners' perception, feelings, and characteristics in an online learning environment?

How does NVC in interactive online learning affect the motivation, level of commitment, and understanding of students?

Methodology

Research Design

A qualitative research method was selected in this study. According to Denzin and Lincoln (2008), qualitative research allows you to delve into the deeper layers of value in people's lives. The qualitative researcher's mission is to find out what those people are saying and doing as a result of their experiences. The study used interview questions as the instrument for obtaining data. The researchers developed interview questions by adopting and adjusting previous researchers' questionnaires.

Procedures

The questions of the semi-structured interview were administered through zoom meetings. The interviewees were invited individually to an online interview, using the Zoom platform which they decided upon, and have them have the chance to decide the time and day to achieve a friendly atmosphere during and before conducting the interview. Pseudonyms are applied to change teachers' names, although some teachers have no problem in revealing their identities. They will henceforward be addressed by teacher 1, teacher 2, teacher 3, etc. Each meeting took 15 minutes. Teachers answered interview questions. Teachers were not guided in any way during the interview. The goal of the interviews was conducting the knowledge and ideas of teachers regarding the topic. In addition, the researcher conducted interviews with students to look at the content of this research from students' perspectives. The researchers asked students to explain their feeling regarding the topic. Students answered interview questions without guidance. The goal of the interviews was to gain a more in-depth understanding of the topic from both perspectives.

Setting and Participants

The research was conducted in an Istanbul-based private chain school. Ten English teachers from four separate campuses of a private primary school took part in this study, which took place in ten distinct classrooms and ten students were interviewed. Teachers' and students' interviews were conducted in a one-on-one question. Each interview took approximately 15 minutes. 50 percent of the participant students were female and 50 percent were male. Students in the classrooms ranged in age from 8 to 9 years old and were native Turkish speakers. The parents were both native Turkish citizens with diverse English backgrounds. All of the teachers that took part in the study were between the ages of 24 and 38. All of the participant teachers in the study were between the ages of 24 and 33. The participants all had a similar English Language Teaching (ELT) educational background. They had 2 to 10 years of teaching experience. Throughout the academic year, they followed the same course and yearly plans. Regarding teaching loads, all of the participant teachers were responsible for

teaching five to seven classes (26-28 hours weekly) each day during the data collection process. The normal class size of this private chain school ranged from 15 -17 students in each class.

Table 1. Participant teachers' demographic information

Participants of the study	Gender	Age	Experience	Education background	Weekly classes	Highest degree	Nationality
Teacher 1	Female	24	2 years	English Language Teaching	26-28 hours	Bachelor	Turkish
Teacher 2	Female	27	4 years	English Language Teaching	26-28 hours	MA in English Language Teaching	Turkish
Teacher 3	Female	29	6 years	English Language Teaching	26-28 hours	MA in English Language Teaching	Turkish
Teacher 4	Male	33	10 years	English Language Teaching	26-28 hours	Bachelor	Turkish
Teacher 5	Female	32	9 years	English Language Teaching	26-28 hours	Bachelor	Turkish
Teacher 6	Male	31	8 years	English Language Teaching	26-28 hours	Bachelor	Turkish
Teacher 7	Female	29	6 years	English Language Teaching	26-28 hours	MA in English Language Teaching	Turkish
Teacher 8	Female	32	10 years	English Language Teaching	26-28 hours	Bachelor	Turkish
Teacher 9	Male	32	10 years	English Language Teaching	26-28 hours	Bachelor	Turkish
Teacher 10	Male	29	6 years	English Language Teaching	26-28 hours	Bachelor	Turkish

Data collection instrument

The semi-structured interview questions in this research were built by the researchers. The questions were selected and adapted from two different surveys which are Al Tawil, R. (2019), and Ismail et al., (2020). A comprehensive method, including two distinct indicators, was used to measure the opinions of teachers about Nonverbal Communication and their presence in interactive online learning, as stated earlier. The first indicator referred to Interview Questions for students includes 8 items and requires students to express their thoughts on how Nonverbal Communication is important for interaction and collaboration in online learning and how the social presence of teachers while using the correct NVC types influence the engagement of learners via open-ended interview questions in the learning process. The second indicator referred to – Interview Questions for Teachers includes seven items and requires teachers to state their thoughts toward the importance of Nonverbal communication in collaborative online teaching, the effects of using appropriate NVC types on students' motivation, and their tactic for overcoming the NVC types of barriers in online teaching.

Data Analysis

Data interpretation has been used to describe the qualitative data obtained from the results of interviews regarding students' and teachers' points of view. As Miles and Huberman (1994) stated the qualitative approach includes the definition, coding, identification, classification, and categorization of the key themes in the data. As for the qualitative data, the researcher and two field experts coded the data separately to ensure inter-rater reliability. The reliability of research was calculated using the Miles and Huberman formula

(Reliability = consensus /consensus + disagreement) and 92 percent in comparisons of the numbers of consensus and disagreement. Miles and Huberman's (1994) formula was used in this study, the agreement between coders which is sufficient to indicate inter-rater reliability is 70 %.

Ethical Considerations

Even though this study did not look at sensitive information about the participants that could violate their privacy, anonymity is being kept. All participants were asked for their consent to take part in the study before they filled in the survey. All parents whose children participated in the study signed an informed consent form. They were informed about the nature of the study (in Turkish) and were informed that they could withdraw from the study at any time.

The Interview Questions for Students' results

Data from the 'Interview Questions for Students' revealed two major themes based on the research questions as follows:

1. Nonverbal Communication (eye contact, tone of voice, and facial expressions) and its impact on the level of understanding.
2. Nonverbal Communication and its effect on the level of motivation.

Theme 1: Students' perceptions regarding the effect of Nonverbal Communication types on comprehension level generated two codes. 2 students reported that the teacher's speed does not affect their comprehension of the topics. Speed of speaking is one of the voice aspects that besides tone and pitch are particularly important to communication. 8 students reported that the teacher's speed affects their comprehension of the topics. They declared that their comprehension level decrease based on the teacher's speaking speed.

St1: "When my teacher talks fast in the online lessons, sometimes I can't understand the topic clearly."

St6: "I can't understand anything because the voice comes like a song"

Theme 2: Students' perceptions regarding the effect of Nonverbal Communication types on motivation level generated one theme. All 10 students noticed that teachers' eye contact and facial expressions are a source of inspiration for them to learn. The lack of teachers' eye contacts non-intentional or intentionally reflected negatively and positively in students' answers:

St1: "When my teacher doesn't look at, the camera or she turns off the camera I feel bad!"

St2: "I feel the teacher doesn't care about us. I can't concentrate on the lesson."

St8: "It is motivational for me. Because I understand better, and it motivates me to be more active in class."

St6: "It is motivational because in online lessons internet is bad and I can't hear something but when the teacher uses his/her body language I can understand."

The Interview Questions for Teachers' results

The Interview Questions for Teachers' results indicated two key themes based on the research questions:

1. The importance of using Nonverbal Communication
2. The effects of NVC on the level of students' motivation
3. Tactics for overcoming Nonverbal Communication barriers

Theme 1: Teachers' perceptions regarding the importance of using Nonverbal Communication in collaborative interaction in online learning. All 9 teachers reported that Nonverbal Communication is essential for collaborative interaction in online learning. They believe that NVC types can be considered as a tool pack to take the students' attention. NVC takes a key role to show the teachers' presence and keeping the students' interaction and collaboration high.

T10: "When we explain ourselves, we mostly use proper body language for making our practices powerful and this is also important for taking the students' attention, sending them some signals for directing their attention to the right point in the lesson and having the collaborative interaction."

T2: "NVC is essential to cover this gap and show the presence of a teacher to keep the interaction between teacher and students collaboratively."

Theme 2: Teachers' perceptions regarding the effects of NVC on the level of students' motivation. All 10 teachers stated that NVC types help the instructor to keep the students interactive, engaged, and motivated in online lessons. It assists teachers to increase the learners' perception and keep the atmosphere of the class much more dynamic.

T4: "It is very essential to engage the learners by using nonverbal language to maintain their attention."

T9: “If the teacher uses NVC skills not effectively, students don’t feel the teacher’s social presence and their motivation in collaborative learning will be decreased.”

Theme 3: Teachers’ perceptions regarding the tactics for overcoming Nonverbal Communication barriers. All 10 teachers indicated that to provide a friendly learning environment teachers shall improve their technology skills for teaching in online classes. Using different kinds of Web 2.0 tools can keep the class and students collaboratively active.

T2: “Third, teachers can use different Web 2.0 tools such as avatars, badges, icons to increase NVC by symbols.”

Based on the analysis the advantages of using Nonverbal Communication efficiently by teachers in their online collaborative learning environment are increasing the student’s motivation and presence and developing the learning achievements. To interpret the quantitative data obtained from surveys, statistical analysis was used. The questionnaire was designed to verify and measure the results of the interview, two variants of the same survey offering a more detailed overview of the research. Answers have been compiled for graphical representation and analysis.

Table 2. Summary of the participant teachers answers to interview questions

Interview questions	Yes	No	Partial y
Do you think that nonverbal communication exists in the synchronous learning environment?	50%	37.5%	12.5%
How important is nonverbal communication in the profession of teaching with students in the synchronous learning environment?	50%	37.5%	12.5%
Is nonverbal communication essential for collaborative interaction in the synchronous learning environment?	80%	10%	10%
Is nonverbal communication important for teachers to express positive emotions in the synchronous learning environment?	90%	0%	10%
Does your nonverbal communication influence students’ motivation and achievement in the synchronous learning environment?	80%	10%	10%
Is there a relationship between teachers’ nonverbal communication and learning outcomes in the synchronous learning environment?	50%	20%	30%
Is there a relationship between teachers’ nonverbal communication and students’ social presence in the synchronous learning environment?	80%	10%	10%

50% of respondents partially agree Nonverbal Communication exists in online learning. 50% of respondents agree that Nonverbal communication is important in the profession of teaching with students in online learning. 80% of respondents strongly agree Nonverbal Communication (NVC) is essential for collaborative interaction in online learning and 90% strongly agree to express more positive emotions in online learning, recognizing Nonverbal Communication by teachers is important.

80% of respondents strongly agree teachers’ Nonverbal Communication affects students’ motivation and achievement. While 50% of respondents agree there is a significant relationship between teachers’ Nonverbal Communication and learning outcomes in online learning 80% of respondents strongly agree there is a significant relationship between student motivation and learning outcomes in online learning and in similarly 80% of respondents strongly agree there is a significant relationship between teachers’ Nonverbal Communication and students’ social presence in online learning.

80% of respondents strongly agree teachers’ Nonverbal Communication can affect the students’ collaboration degree with their friends, Nonverbal Communication affects the students’ level of engagement in collaborative online learning and the teacher’s social presence by using the appropriate NVC effect on students’ interaction in collaborative online learning. 50% of respondents strongly agree students’ NVC can motivate teachers to teach effectively in online sessions. For several reasons, many teachers use hand and facial gestures, as well as other nonverbal communication cues, in various scenarios during a face-to-face class. When students are off task or upsetting their peers, some teachers use nonverbal communication and body language to draw their attention. Other teachers utilize them to emphasize specific concepts or facts that they want their students to pay attention to and understand. Derived from the analysis the highest score proves that teachers’ recognition of their Nonverbal Communication to express more positive emotions in their online learning is very

important. Similarly, it shows teachers' Nonverbal Communication can affect the students' level of engagement in collaborative online learning.

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to demonstrate the relation between Nonverbal Communication (NVC) and teacher presence in collaborative online learning in primary schools. Notably, recent studies have not focused on nonverbal communication in online learning a lot, this gap is tried to be filled in this study. Firstly, Research Question 1 evaluated the relationship between NVC and social presence in a collaborative online learning environment. In the review of the literature, little evidence was found to connect nonverbal communication and teachers' presence in a collaborative online learning environment. Furthermore, the gathered data in this study shows that there is a significant relationship between teachers' nonverbal communication and students' social presence in online learning. The results in this study indicate that there was a significant correlation between teachers' NVC and the social presence of students in an online learning environment. As a result of this study, Nonverbal Communication (NVC) is essential for collaborative interaction in online learning, match this mentioned in earlier studies of some specific nonverbal communication types should be useful to decrease collaborative interaction (Negrón& Antonio Jiménez, 2008; Liman Kaban, 2019). As Gower and Walters (1983) and Ledbury et al. (2004) suggested, eye contact can be used to verify when anyone is focusing, to convey to the student who talks to the instructor, and to promote contributions and involvement. Students also stated that the facial expressions of teachers make them feel happy or unhappy, which is consistent with the views of Ergin and Birol (2005) if a person looks you in the eye, it can be interpreted as caring for you or interested in you, making you feel valued.

Second, Research Question 2 evaluated whether NVC presents in an online learning environment or not. There is no clear answer to this research question. This finding further supports the hypothesis that nonverbal communication has been considered lacking in online courses (Dixson et al., 2017; Liman Kaban, 2021). Moreover, using webcams, headsets and emotional signs, and symbols as a mandatory protocol could reduce the effect of the distance on this kind of unseen communication. Interactive web tools and game-based, learning allows students to be immersed and engaged in the session and NVC could emerge spontaneously.

Lastly, Research Question 3 evaluated the effects of NVC on motivation, level of commitment, and understanding of students in interactive online learning. As it is mentioned in the earlier studies, communication aims to develop motivation in the person to whom addressed (Bambaeroo&Shokrpour, 2017). In the classroom, communication gains more importance to reach the child's understanding and to have an effective and interactive classroom. As mentioned in the data analysis, all of the participant students reported that teachers' eye contact and facial expressions are a source of motivation for them towards the lesson, and this result match with the earlier studies' statements that eye contact encourages students to contribute and participate.

Conclusion and Limitations

Students' nonverbal communication and body language, similar to teachers', are significant elements that on-the-ground instructors regularly utilize to judge their grasp of the lesson, energy level, and motivation, as well as their overall mood. The results have shown that there is a connection between primary EFL teachers' NVC and the forming of student motivation and collaborative engagement. This study discovered that learning happens, but it improves with the presence and motivation supported by teachers' NVC. Eye contact is often viewed by students as a source of inspiration, focus, excitement, and a means to gain attention. Significant learning happens when the attention of students is obtained, based on qualitative researchers, and as Cruickshank et al., (2003) stated cognitive processes start with students paying attention to the cues. If students take part in the class, they are more likely to take actions that improve their comprehension of the subjects as well. The size of the study with poor participation numbers limits the generalizability of the results. Also, time is the biggest limitation of this study. If there was more time, the authors of this study would conduct their research with more participants. Furthermore, the lack of observation of the teachers limits the accurate results for this study, yet more time is needed to observe teachers in their online learning environment and assess their behaviors as regards this study reliably and validly. Since the pandemic has started in early 2020, researchers did not focus on nonverbal communication in online learning environments before. Accordingly, there is a limited number of previous research studies about nonverbal communication in an online learning environment. Moreover, the internet connection speed limited this study's results since there was a lack of talking time while doing interviews with students and learners due to the bad internet connection speed. Accordingly, participants of this study got bored or distracted for this reason.

Other researchers can do this study by observing teachers' online teaching classes. They may ask teachers to record their lessons in two different ways; first, they may ask students to turn on their cameras and they may do their lessons with the cameras on, secondly, the whole class may turn off their cameras and teachers may do the lessons like that. This study is promising research because Nonverbal Communication (NVC) in online

learning is important as a face-to-face class. Although some studies found that, some students considered online learning as more attractive than face-to-face because there is a lack of Nonverbal Communication. They transformed the lack of Nonverbal Communication and found different ways to connect to their teachers and friends. Meanwhile, other students considered it hard to learn new things without Nonverbal Communication and its reinforcement.

References

- Allen, M., Witt, P., & Wheelless, L. (2006). The Role of Teacher Immediacy as a Motivational Factor in Student Learning: Using Meta-Analysis to Test a Causal Model. *Communication Education*, 55(1), 21-31. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03634520500343368>
- Al Tawil, R. (2019). Nonverbal Communication in Text-Based, Asynchronous Online Education. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 20(1). <https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v20i1.3705>
- Akyol, Z., & Garrison, D. R. (2008). The development of a community of inquiry over time in an online course: Understanding the progression and integration of social, cognitive and teaching presence. *Journal of Asynchronous Learning Networks*, 12(2-3), 3-23.
- Andersen, J.F., Andersen, P.A. & Jensen, A.D. (1979). The measurement of immediacy. *Journal of Applied Communication Research*, 7, 153-180.
- Bambaerero, F., & Shokrpour, N. (2017). The impact of the teachers' non-verbal communication on success in teaching. *Journal of advances in medical education & professionalism*, 5(2), 51.,
- Bunglowala, A & Bunglowala, A. (2015). Nonverbal communication: An integral part of the teaching learning process. *International Journal of Research in Advent Technology Special Issue 1st International Conference on Advent Trends in Engineering*. Science and Technology 8 Maret "ICATEST 2015", 371-375.
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach* (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Cruickshank, D., Jenkins, D. B., Metcalf, K. K., (2003). *The Act of Teaching*. Third Edition. McGraw Hill Companies.
- Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (2008). *The landscape of qualitative research* (3rd ed.). Sage Publications.
- Devito, J. (2007). *The interpersonal communication book* (11th ed.). Pearson.
- Dixon, M. D., Greenwell, M. R., Rogers-Stacy, C., Weister, T., & Lauer, S. (2017). Nonverbal immediacy behaviors and online student engagement: Bringing past instructional research into the present virtual classroom. *Communication Education*, 66(1), 37-53.
- Ergin, A., & Birol, C., (2005). *Eğitimde İletişim*. Anı Yayıncılık.
- Garrison, D. R., Anderson T., & Archer, W. (2000). Critical inquiry in a text-based environment: Computer conferencing in higher education. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 2(2-3), 87-105. Retrieved from http://cde.athabascau.ca/coi_site/documents/Garrison_Anderson_Archer_Critical_Inquiry_model.pdf
- Griffin, V. (1985). A survey of the use of nonverbal communication by primary teachers in class management. *UNF Digital Commons*. Retrieved from: <http://digitalcommons.unf.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?articles=1043&context=etd>
- Hackman, M. Z., & Walker, K. B. (1990). Instructional communication in the televised classroom: The effects of system design and teacher immediacy on student learning and satisfaction. *Communication Education*, 39(3), 196-206. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03634529009378802>
- Hsieh, H. F., & Shannon, S. E. (2005). Three approaches to qualitative content analysis. *Qualitative health research*, 15(9), 1277-1288.
- Ismail, Z., Halias, N., Saad, R., & Mohamed, M. (2020). Motivation as the Mediator in Relationship between Non-verbal Communication of Arabic Language Teachers and Student Learning Outcomes. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(2), 700-708. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2020.080244>
- Khalil, R., Mansour, A., Fadda, W., Almisnid, K., Aldamegh, M., & Al-Nafeesah, A. et al. (2020). The sudden transition to synchronized online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic in Saudi Arabia: a qualitative study exploring medical students' perspectives. *BMC Medical Education*, 20(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-020-02208-z>
- Ledbury, R. et al., (2004). The Importance of Eye Contact in the Classroom. *The Internet TESL Journal*, volume X, No. 8 <http://iteslj.org>
- Liman Kaban, A. (2019). Kişilerarası İletişimdede duygusal bulaşmanın rolü: öğretmen öğrenci iletişimi üzerine bir araştırma/The role of emotional contagion in interpersonal communication: a research on teacher-student communication. *Maltepe Üniversitesi İletişim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 6 (1), 87-108. Retrieved from <http://dergipark.org.tr/iled/issue/47108/592539>

- Liman Kaban, A. (2021). YAITIS: The Design and Development of a Personalized E-Book Platform for EFL Learners. In Giannikas, C. N. (Eds.), *Teaching Practices and Equitable Learning in Children's Language Education* (pp. 171-190). IGI Global. <http://doi:10.4018/978-1-7998-6487-5.ch009>.
- Manusov, V. (2016). A history of research on nonverbal communication: Our divergent pasts and their contemporary legacies. In D. Matsumoto, H. C. Hwang, & M. G. Frank (Eds.), *APA handbook of nonverbal communication* (pp. 3-15). Washington, DC: American Psychological Association. doi: [10.1037/14669-001](https://doi.org/10.1037/14669-001)
- Marshall, C., & Rossman, G. B. (1989). *Designing qualitative research*. Sage.
- Mehrabian, A. (1981). *Silent messages: Implicit communication of emotions and attitudes*. Wadsworth.
- Miles, M. B., & Huberman, A. M. (1994). *Qualitative data analysis: An expanded sourcebook* (2nd ed.). Sage Publications.
- Negrón, A. P. P., & de Antonio Jiménez, A. (2008). *Nonverbal Communication to Support Collaborative Interaction in Collaborative Virtual Environments for Learning*.
- Pierce, J., (2020). But What about Nonverbal Communication? A Look at Interactions Online. *Model ELearning*. Retrieved from 17 Feb. 2020, modelelearning.com/2020/02/18/but-what-about-nonverbal-communication-a-look-at-interactions-online/.
- Reilly, J. R., Gallagher-Lepak, S., & Killion, C. (2012). Me and my computer: emotional factors in online learning. *Nursing Education Perspectives*, 33(2), 100-106.
- Richardson, J., Maeda, Y., Lv, J., & Caskurlu, S. (2017). Social presence in relation to students' satisfaction and learning in the online environment: A meta-analysis. *Computers In Human Behavior*, 71, 402-417. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2017.02.001>
- Richmond, V. P., & McCroskey, J. C. (2000). *Nonverbal behavior in interpersonal relations* (4th ed.). Allyn & Bacon.
- Wolfgang, A. (1977). The silent language in the multicultural classroom. *Theory into Practice*, 16, 145-155.

Author Information

Ayşegül Liman Kaban
